

Original Research Article

Factors Affecting Classroom Participation in Undergraduate Nursing Students at Private Colleges of Nursing Lahore

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Abstract

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Classroom participation is more than just a question-and-answer session with the professor. Classroom participation is the extent to which a student participates in class discussions by answering questions. It is referred to as a wider notion in which a student's class preparation, attendance, and contribution, as well as skills like group and communication skills are all included. The main purpose of this study was to examine the factors that affect class participation at different private colleges of nursing Lahore. A cross sectional descriptive survey was conducted. A convenient sample of 300 Nursing Students was recruited. Data was collected through a closed ended self-administered questionnaire. The data was analyzed through SPSS 21 version. The data was analyzed in the form of Frequencies, graphs and tables. The results of this current study indicate that class participation of Nursing Students of the selected at different private Colleges of Nursing in Lahore were influenced by different factors like only 06% agreed that they do not participate in class because of lack of confidence, 32% agreed that they do not participate due to lack of preparation, 17% were afraid of speaking in front of class, a good number 30% stated that they participate in class when teachers provide them equal opportunities. Overall the findings revealed that the participants gave mostly responses in not agreeing the factors that can influence their classroom participation and affect their study

Keywords: Factors, Classroom participation, Nursing Students

INTRODUCTION

The health-care delivery system, which includes many subfields, including nursing, is one of the basic pillars of every country's economy. Nursing has been described as "very dynamic" because it changes on a daily basis. There are many factors that contribute to this, including: Changing population health care needs, expanding research, and the growing role of technology in health care among other things, wellbeing.

As a result, problem-solving skills are needed to address congenital challenges and to integrate new knowledge and technologies that may impact care. The Nursing Unit can help students develop problem-solving skills by promoting student-centered teaching practices that promote active learning and active participation in the classroom. (Tedesco-Schneck, 2016).

Classroom participation is more than just a question-

and-answer session with the professor. It has been described from a variety of perspectives; some definitions have focused solely on what happens in the classroom, while others have expanded beyond that. It is defined as a student's voluntary contribution in class that starts with the student raising his or her hand in class to provide the required comments (Abeasi, 2019).

Classroom participation is the extent to which a student participates in class discussions by answering questions. It is referred to as a wider notion in which a student's class preparation, attendance, and contribution, as well as skills like group and communication skills, are all included. Classroom engagement and active learning go hand in hand. Class participation is required for effective learning to take place. Classroom activities that develop participatory knowledge-sharing environments are known as active learning (Aziz et al., 2018).

Classroom participation is linked to positive learning outcomes. Students who took part found that group members improved their communication skills. In a democratic society, interactions and functioning are important. It helps the situation once more. Level of self-assurance when classroom participation is high, rote learning is minimized. This is because participation provides the student with the ability to understand, interpret, synthesize, and interpret information after receiving it. Communication, critical thinking, and self-assurance are all crucial in preparing student nurses for their future careers and lives (Rocca, 2010).

Educators have concentrated their efforts on developing a variety of techniques to improve student participation in response to low participation rates. Some educators assign grades or points to participation as part of the overall evaluation of the student in order to promote participation. Others call students at random, which means that participation is forced rather than voluntary in this case. Some educators have also attempted to shift from teacher-centered to more student-centered teaching methods that allow for participation. The current research looked at the factors that influence undergraduate nursing students' classroom participation.

Problem Statement

Active learning requires active participation in the classroom. Though active participation is not the only criterion for determining whether students have grasped concepts, it does provide a platform for input that allows the lecturer to determine whether students have gained some understanding. In addition to the foregoing, despite the importance often placed on classroom participation, most students remain passive in class for personal reasons. As a result, this has an impact on the teaching and learning process.

Ineffective participation in the classroom usually leads to boredom, and those who do not participate may not

pay attention. Such students are often disadvantaged because they have to memorize additional information, are less likely to be able to read and debate information, are less motivated, do not develop their oral communication skills, and lack confidence.

Purpose of the Study

The study's goal is to look at how student, faculty, and classroom environment influences classroom involvement among undergraduate nursing students at different private nursing colleges in Lahore.

Objectives of the Study

Main Objective

The main aim of the study is to examine factors affecting classroom participation in Undergraduate nursing students at different private nursing colleges in Lahore.

Specific Objectives

- I. Determining student characteristics that affect the participation of students at different private nursing colleges in Lahore.
- II. To find out faculty factors affecting classroom participation of undergraduate nursing Students at different private nursing colleges in Lahore.
- III. To identify classroom factors affecting classroom participation of undergraduate nursing Students at different private nursing colleges in Lahore.
- IV. To identify the relationship between classroom participation and the students' demographic variables.

Research Questions

- I. What are the students' factors affecting classroom participation of undergraduate nursing Students at different private nursing colleges in Lahore?
- II. What factors of the faculty affect classroom participation of undergraduate Students at different private nursing colleges in Lahore?
- III. What classroom related factors affect classroom participation of undergraduate Students at different private nursing colleges in Lahore?
- IV. What is the relationship between class participation and students statistical variability?

Significance of the Study

The results of this study will attempt to shed light on the

factors that influence undergraduate students' class participation.

First and foremost, a better understanding of the variables that affect classroom involvement will help faculty formulate and execute strategies to actively involve nursing students in the class.

Nursing faculty would use this information to build classroom settings that encourage student involvement in order to help them develop problem-solving skills in preparation for the complex health-care environment they may encounter.

In addition to the foregoing, the current research would inform students about the variables that stimulate or discourage their involvement in asking lecturers' questions and offering input on their lecturers' questions.

As a result, they will attempt to overcome those barriers in order to effectively engage in classroom question-and-answer sessions as well as classroom conversations.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The descriptive design of the cross-sectional study was used to identify factors influencing class participation among graduate nursing students.

Research Setting

The setting for the study was four different private nursing colleges of Lahore.

Target Population

The population for the study was all nursing students at four different private nursing colleges in Lahore.

Inclusion Criteria

- Only BSN nursing students from these nursing colleges.
- Students who will give their consent have been included in the study.

Exclusion Criteria

- Students of Post RN, MSN will be excluded from the study.
- Students who will not give consent to participate in the study.

Sampling method and sample size

Sampling method

The sample was obtained by using the convenient probability sampling method.

Sample size

A sample size of 300 undergraduate nursing students was selected for the study which consisted of BSN students.

Data Collection

Method of Data Collection

Data was collected with the use of a close ended adopted self-administered questionnaire. First of all permission was taken from the Director of Nursing Saida Waheed FMH College of Nursing. The study purpose was explained to the participants. Then the questionnaires were distributed to each participant along with an informed consent where it was filled and returned back to the researchers by each participant.

Tool for Data Collection

Data was collected with the use of a close ended adopted self-administered questionnaire. The Questionnaire contains 35 items which are grouped into four sections.

- I. Section A deals with the demographic data of the respondents which included the age, gender and class level of the participants.
- II. Section B deals with the student factors that influence classroom participation.
- III. Section C deals with faculty factors influencing classroom participation.
- IV. Section D deals with classroom climate factors influencing classroom participation. The questionnaire includes close ended questions in which respondents are provided with options to select.

Data Analysis

Data were analyzed using the Social Sciences Mathematical Package (SPSS Version 21). Descriptive statistics were used. Results are presented in tables and graphs

Table 1. Demographic data findings

Variables	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
Gender		
1. Male	60	20
2. Female	240	80
Age (Years)		
1. 16-20	21	07
2. 21-25	264	88
3. 26-30	12	04
4. >30 years	3	01
Marital Status		
1. Married	9	03
2. Unmarried	291	97
Religion		
1. Muslim	240	80
2. Christian	60	20

Validity and Reliability

Validity

Validity is checked in the previous study by examining and correcting the questionnaire by the supervisors before field operation.

Reliability

Reliability is also checked by the previous research study to ensure that high quality data collection instruments were used during the fieldwork period.

Ethical consideration

- ✓ Approval of research ethics will be obtained from the Saida Waheed FMH CON Lahore Ethics Review Committee.
- ✓ Permission from the head of department and programs coordinators will be granted before conducting this study.
- ✓ No personal identity of participants will be revealed.
- ✓ A consent form will be attached with each questionnaire.
- ✓ No participant will be forced to participate in the research work.
- ✓ All confidential information must be kept confidential.

RESULTS

Demographic Information

Table 1 focuses on the demographic characteristics of undergraduate nursing students. Specifically, the age,

Gender and religion are being studied under this research.

The results in table 1 showed that most of the respondents (80%) were females. It is not surprising that most of the respondents were females because nursing is perceived as a female related profession; hence a lot of females apply to pursue nursing as a profession. Furthermore, the majority of respondents (88%) were between 16-20 years, 4% were between 26-30 years and another 1% was above 30 years. A huge majority 97% were unmarried and only 3% were married. Moreover, as high as 80% of respondents were Muslims whereas 20% were Christians. These nursing colleges are from Lahore and located in Muslim based population and usually more Muslims are enrolled than other religions.

Student Factors Affecting Classroom Participation

Results from Table 2 show that, 06% of respondents strongly agree that they do not participate in class because they do not have the confidence to do so, 09% agreed, 30% disagreed, 34% strongly disagreed while 21% were neutral. The responses of the participants, 8% strongly agreed and (32%) agreed, 36% were neutral, 18% disagreed and 06% strongly disagreed that inadequate preparation before the lecture hindered their ability to participate in class. To the 3rd question, 6% of respondents strongly agreed that they were afraid of speaking in front of class which prevented them from participating, 17% agreed, 16% were neutral, 48% disagreed whilst 13% strongly disagreed. Same way, 3% of respondents strongly agreed that they are afraid of being unintelligent, to participate in class, 15% agreed, and 15% were neutral, and 41% disagreed whereas 26% strongly disagreed. Furthermore, 14% agreed that they had low self-esteem, so they are unable to participate in classroom discussion, 51% disagreed and 27% strongly

Table 2. Student factors affecting classroom participation

S. No	Variables	SA f(%)	A f(%)	N f(%)	D f(%)	SD f(%)
1.	I do not participate in class because I do not have the confidence to do so	18 (06)	27 (09)	63 (21)	90 (30)	102 (34)
2.	Inadequate preparation before the lecture hinders my ability to participate in class	24 (08)	96 (32)	108 (36)	54 (18)	18 (06)
3.	I am afraid of speaking in front of the whole class and it prevent me from participating	18 (06)	51 (17)	48 (16)	144 (48)	39 (13)
4.	I am afraid of appearing unintelligent, so I do not participate in class	9 (03)	45 (15)	45 (15)	123 (41)	78 (26)
5.	I have a low self-esteem so I am unable to participate in classroom discussion	3 (01)	42 (14)	21 (07)	153 (51)	81 (27)
6.	I do not have control over English language which is the main means of communication, hence I do not participate in class	12 (04)	36 (12)	60 (20)	135 (45)	57 (19)
7.	I am often shy of my course mates so I do not participate in class	06 (02)	39 (13)	42 (14)	156 (52)	57 (19)
8.	I am afraid of negative evaluation from colleagues so I do not participate	12 (04)	63 (21)	39 (13)	132 (44)	54 (18)
9.	I desire to remain anonymous especially to my lectures so I do not like participation in class	21 (07)	18 (06)	75 (25)	138 (46)	48 (16)
10.	I am not motivated to participate in class	03 (01)	36 (12)	45 (15)	153 (51)	63 (21)
11.	When some students dominate the classroom participation, it does not encourage me to participate	15 (05)	24 (08)	51 (17)	144 (48)	66 (22)
12.	I do not participate because I do not perceive classroom participation as important	06 (02)	18 (06)	57 (19)	144 (48)	75 (25)
13.	I do not participate when I perceive the course is not interesting	12 (04)	51 (17)	87 (29)	105 (35)	45 (15)

*SA= Strongly Agree, A= Agree, N= Neutral, D=Disagree, SD= Strongly Disagree, f= Frequency

disagreed. In addition to the above, 4% of respondents strongly agree that they have no control over the English language which is the main means of communication, which is why they do not participate in class, 12% agreed, 45% disagreed, whilst 19% strongly disagreed. Also, 13% of respondents agreed that they are often shy of their course mates so they do not participate in class, 14% were neutral, 52% disagreed and 19% strongly disagreed. Regarding the desire for anonymity, 46% and 16% of respondents disagreed and strongly argued that they wished anonymity especially to their teachers so that they would not want to participate in class, only 7% strongly agreed, 6% agreed and 25% were neutral. On negative evaluation from colleagues, 21% and 04% of respondents agreed and strongly agreed that they were afraid of negative evaluation from colleagues so they did not participate, 13% were neutral, 44% disagreed and 18% strongly disagreed. Concerning motivation, 51% disagreed, 21% strongly disagreed that they are not motivated to participate in class and only 06% of respondents agreed to perceive classroom participation importance, respondent 48% strongly disagreed and 25% disagreed that they do not participate because they do not perceive classroom participation as important. 19% of the participants remained neutral. Lastly, respondents strongly disagreed (15%) and disagreed (35%) that they

do not participate when they perceive the course is not interesting. Thus, the participation of the majority of the respondents (29%) was not affected by the interesting nature of the course.

Findings of the above table 3 revealed that, 11% of respondents strongly agreed that they participate in class when the lecturer offers equal opportunities for us to participate, 30% agreed, 31% disagreed, 5% strongly disagreed whilst 23% remained neutral. Of the participants, 06% agreed, 15% were neutral, 59% disagreed and 20% strongly disagreed that they participate when the lecturer usually builds on their contributions and does not criticize them. To another question, 7% of respondents strongly agreed that they participate when the lecturer is of the same gender, 42% agreed, 32% were neutral, 16% disagreed whilst 03% strongly disagreed. Similarly, 20% of respondents strongly agree that they participate when the facilitator provides sufficient waiting time to process information and provide feedback, 37% agreed, 19% were neutral, 22% disagreed whereas 02% strongly disagreed. Furthermore, 16% of respondents strongly agreed that they participate when the lecturer mentions their name to contribute, 51% agreed, 21% were neutral, 08% disagreed and 04% strongly disagreed. In addition to the above, 21% of respondents strongly agreed that they participate when

Figure 1. Showed that 21% and 4% of respondents agreed and strongly agreed that they were afraid of negative evaluation from colleagues so they did not participate, 13% were neutral, 44% disagreed and 18% strongly disagreed.

Table 3. Faculty Factors affecting classroom participation

Sr#	Variables	SA	A	N	D	SD
		f(%)	f(%)	f(%)	f(%)	f(%)
1.	I participate when the lecturer offers equal opportunities for us to participate	33 (11)	90 (30)	69 (23)	93 (31)	15 (05)
2.	I participate when the lecturer usually builds on my contributions but does not condemn or criticize me	00 (00)	18 (06)	45 (15)	177 (59)	60 (20)
3.	I participate when the lecturer and I are of the same gender (male-male or female-female)	21 (07)	126 (42)	96 (32)	48 (16)	09 (03)
4.	I do participate when the lecturer gives adequate wait time for us to digest information and give comments	60 (20)	111 (37)	57 (19)	66 (22)	06 (02)
5.	I participate when the lecturer mentions my name to contribute	48 (16)	153 (51)	63 (21)	24 (08)	12 (04)
6.	I participate when lecturer awards marks for classroom participation	63 (21)	144 (48)	72 (24)	15 (05)	06 (02)
7.	I participate when the lecturer asks open ended or analytical questions	27 (09)	114 (38)	105 (35)	42 (14)	12 (04)
8.	I do not participate when the lecturer is unfriendly	27 (09)	84 (28)	87 (29)	84 (28)	18 (06)
9.	I do not participate when the lecturer is boring	33 (11)	90 (30)	75 (25)	87 (29)	15 (05)
10.	I do not participate when the lecturer likes embarrassing student in front of classmates	57 (19)	108 (36)	72 (24)	42 (14)	21 (07)

lecturer awards marks for classroom participation, 48% agreed, 24% neutral, 05% disagreed, whilst 02% strongly disagreed. Also, 9% strongly agreed, 38% of respondents agreed that they participate when the lecturer asks open ended or analytical questions, 35% were neutral, 14% disagreed and 04% strongly disagreed. On asking when the lecturer is unfriendly, 28% and 6% of the respondents disagreed and strongly disagreed that they do not participate when the lecturer is unfriendly, 09% strongly agreed, 28% agreed and 29% were neutral. On negative evaluation from colleagues, 30% and 11% of

respondents agreed and strongly agreed that they do not participate when the lecturer is boring, 25% were neutral, 29% disagreed and 05% strongly disagreed. Regarding the embarrassment, 14% did not agree, 7% did not agree at all that they did not participate when the teacher humiliated the student in front of his classmates.. 36% of respondents agreed, 19% strongly agreed whilst 25% were neutral. Figure 1, Table 3

Findings of the above table revealed that, 11% of respondents strongly agreed that they participate in class when the lecturer offers equal opportunities for us to

Figure 2. Show that 11% of respondents strongly agreed that they participate in class when the lecturer offers equal opportunities for us to participate, 30% agreed, 31% disagreed, 5% strongly disagreed whilst 23% remained neutral.

Table 4. Classroom factors affecting classroom participation

Sr #	Variables	SA f(%)	A f(%)	N f(%)	D f(%)	SD f(%)
1	I am reluctant to participate in the traditional classroom setting	27 (09)	48 (16)	150 (50)	48 (16)	27 (09)
	I am reluctant to participate in large class	15 (05)	60 (20)	135 (45)	57 (19)	33 (11)
	I feel nervous when I am sitting in front of the class, so I do not participate	33 (11)	42 (14)	66 (22)	114 (38)	45 (15)
	I do not participate when the lecture is in the late afternoon because I will be exhausted by then	36 (12)	93 (31)	54 (18)	96 (32)	21 (07)
	I feel uncomfortable when the classroom is very warm so I do not participate	27 (09)	81 (27)	60 (20)	99 (33)	33 (11)

participate, 30% agreed, 31% disagreed, 5% strongly disagreed whilst 23% remained neutral. Of the participants, 06% agreed, 15% were neutral, 59% disagreed and 20% strongly disagreed that they participate when the lecturer usually builds on their contributions and does not criticize them. To another question, 7% of respondents strongly agreed that they participate when the lecturer is of the same gender, 42% agreed, 32% were neutral, 16% disagreed whilst 03% strongly disagreed. Similarly, 20% of respondents strongly agree that they participate when the facilitator provides sufficient waiting time to process information and provide feedback, 37% agreed, 19% were neutral, 22% disagreed whereas 02% strongly disagreed. Furthermore, 16% of respondents strongly agreed that they participate when the lecturer mentions their name to contribute, 51% agreed, 21% were neutral, 08% disagreed and 04% strongly disagreed. In addition to the above, 21% of respondents strongly agreed that they participate when lecturer awards marks for classroom

participation, 48% agreed, 24% neutral, 05% disagreed, whilst 02% strongly disagreed. Also, 9% strongly agreed, 38% of respondents agreed that they participate when the lecturer asks open ended or analytical questions, 35% were neutral, 14% disagreed and 04% strongly disagreed. On asking when the lecturer is unfriendly, 28% and 6% of the respondents disagreed and strongly disagreed that they do not participate when the lecturer is unfriendly, 09% strongly agreed, 28% agreed and 29% were neutral. On negative evaluation from colleagues, 30% and 11% of respondents agreed and strongly agreed that they do not participate when the lecturer is boring, 25% were neutral, 29% disagreed and 05% strongly disagreed. Regarding the embarrassment, 14% did not agree, 7% did not agree at all that they did not participate when the teacher humiliated the student in front of his classmates.. 36% of respondents agreed, 19% strongly agreed whilst 25% were neutral. Figure 2, Table 4

Table 4 revealed that 16% and 9% of the respondents

Figure 3. Show that Concerning feeling nervous when sitting in class, 38% disagreed, 15% strongly disagreed that they feel nervous when sitting in class thus they do not participate. Only 14% of respondents agreed, 11% strongly agreed whilst 22% were neutral.

disagreed and strongly disagreed that they feel reluctant to participate in a traditional class setting, only 9% strongly agreed, 16% agreed while 50% were neutral. On reluctance to participate in a large class, 20% and 05% of respondents agreed and strongly agreed that they feel reluctant to participate in a large class, 45% were neutral, 19% disagreed and 11% strongly disagreed. Concerning feeling nervous when sitting in class, 38% disagreed, 15% strongly disagreed that they feel nervous when sitting in class thus they do not participate. Only 14% of respondents agreed, 11% strongly agreed whilst 22% were neutral. On lectures in late afternoon classes, 07% respondents strongly disagreed and 32% disagreed that they do not participate because they feel exhausted in late afternoon classes. 18% of the participants remained neutral while 32% agreed and 11% strongly agreed to the statement. Lastly, respondents strongly disagreed (11%) and disagreed (33%) that they do not participate in class when it is warm. 20% participants were neutral, 27% agreed and 09% strongly agreed to the statement. Figure 3

DISCUSSIONS

The quality of undergraduate students' classroom performance is influenced by a number of factors. The current study focuses on some of the aspects that may influence students' performance in the classroom. This study showed that 80% participants were female because nursing was preserved as a female related profession .88% of them belonged to the age group 21 to 25 years

old. But in the previous study that was conducted in Lahore Pakistan, in which 85.3% female participated. (Mushtaq et al., 2019). Another study conducted in 2016 where 73.4% of the respondents were female. This could be due to the fact that originally the nursing course was for female students, so the male students are few (Nalwanga, 2016).

In this study total 17% student agree about that they are afraid to speaking in front of their class and the speaking issue leads all problem like the reason of their shyness, their low confident and their self-esteem. The other study that was conducted in Ghana shows that 54% student afraid to speak in front of their class. If we compare our current study to the previous study the ratio was decreased. That means our new generation builds their confidence and speaking skills. (Abeasi and AdjeiKwakwa, 2020)

Present study showed that only 12% reported that they do not have command over the English language which affected their level of participation. That is the other factor that lowers their confidence level and their speaking skills. But compared to a 2016 past survey in which 5 out of 10 students expressed that since English was their second language they felt free to express their thoughts which means that 50% of the students were not free to express his or her thoughts. In English why they did not want to participate in the class but in the current study the rate has dropped. (Susak, 2016).

In our current study show that 42% participator said they participate in lecture when the gender was same that's mean they feel shyness toward other gender but we compare it to past study that was held in 2020 the

ratio was increased .in the past study only 15% student participate in lecture when gender was same. In the same study 42% responded that they don't participate in lecture if the lecturer is unfriendly but in the current study only 28% of students responded that the friendly nature matters in class participation, which was another huge difference. (Abeasi and AdjeiKwakwa, 2020).

The current study found that the majority 51% of students were likely to participate when their names were mentioned by the lecturer. Similar findings were found in a previous study where the participants reported that they like to participate when their names are mentioned (Abeasi&AdjeiKwakwa, 2020). On the contrary, another study reported that students get more anxious when called upon to respond individually (Sholihah, 2019). Moreover, in present study it was found that 48% of students were likely to participate when marks were awarded for that. In a similar way in a past research study, the majority of nursing students participated when marks were awarded for that. No student would like to lose marks especially if it affected their overall grade (Susak, 2016). Similarly, it was also found that class participation increased when associated with course credits (Abeasi&AdjeiKwakwa, 2020).

20% of students respond that they do not participate because of the large number of students and 45% said it's neutral. The 20% of the respondents were unwilling to participate in large classrooms, according to the data. Some students may not engage in large classrooms for a variety of reasons. To begin with, it is likely to locate the frequent participants, leading other pupils to believe that even if they do not participate, others will. Others, too, suffer from stage fright, particularly while performing in front of the entire class. On the other hand, if the class is tiny, you may be the only one who can participate. In a similar study, students said that smaller class sizes and small groups helped them learn more. (Susak, 2016).

CONCLUSION

Classroom involvement has gotten a lot of excellent attention, and it's not completely unjustified because it helps students to acquire the ability to think critically and practical problem-solving skills. These skills will be valuable in their professional development and other aspects of self-improvement. Because nursing students need to be confident about their abilities and their skills. The findings of this study provide some insight into the elements impacting engagement among students, lecturers, and classroom climate. In this study the confidence level of students is good. They have no issues dealing with their confidence except teacher gender, most of them not feeling comfortable around the opposite gender and on the other side the large number

of classes is also another factor. Because mostly students discuss in small groups and understand the things easily.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on above findings following recommendations are needed:

The lecturers in the colleges should encourage students, this is likely to boost the confidence of students to speak in class, negative evaluations and comments by classmates should be condemned by lecturers to make room for low esteemed and shy students to be able to participate in class.

Students should take upon themselves to adequately prepare themselves before lectures so that they are not found in an uncomfortable situation. Students should also foster good relationships amongst each other, be friendly and give motivation to each other.

The management of the colleges should provide a conducive atmosphere for learning by providing good, comfortable furniture and learning materials for students and lecturers to work with. Large class sizes can be divided in smaller sizes to foster participation.

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